

E4S
ENERGY4SUPPLY

Dissemination and communication plan

Deliverable 5.1

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Lead Beneficiary	Polar Energy Solutions AB		
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DISCLAIMER

ENERGY4SUPPLY has received funding from the European Union’s LIFE23-CET-BUSINESS programme under grant agreement no. 101167263. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency, CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document, the Dissemination and Communication Plan (Deliverable D5.1), contains a plan that outlines how the E4S project will work with dissemination and communication throughout the entire project timeline. The objective of the dissemination and communication plan is to ensure that the results of the E4S project are disseminated and communicated appropriately to the defined stakeholders and target groups. A multi-level and multi-channel approach will be adopted to engage stakeholders and target groups in a strategic manner, with awareness-raising activities being carried out to reach all other project beneficiaries.

The document describes the dissemination and communication objectives and how these objectives are to be achieved through the work within specific tasks led by different project beneficiaries in collaboration, so to ensure effective dissemination and communication with and to key stakeholders and target groups as identified in the stakeholder analysis. Deliverables that will be generated as well as specific milestones. The budgeted efforts to be used in as described specific dissemination and communication activities.

A methodology is presented and specific dissemination and communication channels introduced that will be utilized based on the direction of the dissemination and communication working group that will meet regularly. A timeline that spans across the entire project life cycle is also presented and will be elaborated on as the project interacts more and more with its key stakeholders and target groups. Important information about how the EU should be made visible in the work is also presented.

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Project summary

The overall scope of the E4S project is to drive the clean energy transition forward within the supply chain of the manufacturing sector, by focusing on enhancing the energy efficiency of the small- and medium sized enterprise (SME) suppliers within a manufacturing industry's supply chain. The project directly addresses the urgent global need for sustainable energy practices and aims to significantly reduce carbon emissions by integrating SMEs into a broader decarbonization effort.

The central objective of the E4S project is to develop and implement a novel certification scheme tailored specifically for SMEs, which simplifies and enhances the assessment of energy efficiency. This scheme departs from traditional, burdensome certifications like ISO 50001, offering a lighter, more adaptable alternative. The project is set against a backdrop of pressing environmental challenges, where SMEs often struggle with the complexity and costs associated with standard energy efficiency measures.

Key activities of the project are to (1) developing a ranking system to evaluate suppliers based on their energy efficiency. (2) Establishing energy efficiency networks that foster collaborative learning and sharing of best practices. (3) Creating a centralized resource hub to support SMEs in implementing sustainable energy solutions.

Main achievements and expected results of the project are (1) A transformative certification system that motivates and recognizes SMEs for energy-efficient practices. (2) Increased adoption of energy management systems across the SME sector, with a target of a 50% implementation rate of energy audit recommendations. (3) Strengthened capacities of SMEs to engage in sustainable practices, enhancing their competitiveness and sustainability.

Through these strategic actions, the E4S project aims to catalyse a shift in the manufacturing sector towards more sustainable and economically viable energy practices. By empowering focal companies to act as catalysts for change within their supply chains, the project creates a ripple effect that enhances the overall sustainability of the industry.

1.2. Scope of this document

The purpose of elaborating the E4S dissemination and communication plan is to specify the objective, approach, target group, key actors, channels and tools to ensure the smooth implementation of all communication and dissemination related activities of the E4S project during and after the project life cycle.

This deliverable corresponds to Task T5.1 of the Technical Annex. For practical purposes, dissemination actions should spread information about results obtained during the project, i.e. conclusions, recommendations and objectives

accomplished. Here, feedback from the target audience is not required. In contrast, communication actions should send messages about our current status, benefits, challenges faced and intentions and that requires feedback from potential stakeholders and target audiences in general. There is a close alliance between dissemination and communication.

This document has been prepared in the first three months of the E4S project at the end of 2024 and beginning of 2025 and outlines a detailed plan for Dissemination and Communication.

1.3. Objectives

No	Objective
1	Ensure Comprehensive Dissemination of Project Findings and Knowledge: Develop and execute a detailed dissemination plan, encompassing scientific publications, workshops, trainings, webinars, and a comprehensive digital handbook, to ensure that project knowledge and results are accessible to all relevant stakeholders.
2	Maximize Stakeholder Engagement Through Diverse Channels: Engage a broad range of stakeholders, including policy makers, industry stakeholders, academic community, and the general public, through targeted channels like direct email campaigns, industry forums, academic journals, social media, and public webinars.
3	Promote Visibility of EU Funding: Strictly adhere to guidelines for highlighting EU funding support, featuring the EU logotype prominently in all communications and integrating messages about EU support across various platforms, including the project website, newsletters, and public engagements.
4	Foster Collaborations and Networking Opportunities: Actively collaborate with other EU projects and industry associations, co-creating events and content, and aligning with objectives for mutual benefit.
5	Ensure Effective Monitoring and Evaluation of Communication Activities: Implement monitoring methods where relevant like web analytics, email analytics, and social media analytics to track engagement metrics such as website visits, newsletter reach, and social media engagement.

1.4. Tasks

Task	Title	Description	Responsibility	Timeline
5.1	Dissemination & Communication Plan	This task involves the development of a detailed and dynamic dissemination	Lead: PES	M1 – M36

Deliverable D5.1 – Dissemination and Communication Plan

		<p>and communication plan. The plan will:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Include targeted strategies for different stakeholder groups, such as policy makers, industry stakeholders, academic community, and the general public. 2. Outline specific channels and approaches for each target audience, ensuring tailored and effective dissemination and communication. 3. Emphasize adherence to EU funding visibility guidelines, ensuring consistent integration of EU support messaging across all platforms. 	<p>Support: Partners</p> <p>All</p>	
5.2	Dissemination and Communication Activities	<p>This task focuses on executing a variety of dissemination and communication activities, as outlined in the Dissemination and communication Plan (T.5.1), to effectively share project findings. Activities include:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Organizing interactive workshops, with a focus on engaging industry stakeholders and policy makers. 2. Publishing findings in peer-reviewed journals and industry-specific trade publications. 3. Creating high-quality, informative online 	<p>Lead: PES</p> <p>Support: Partners</p> <p>All</p>	M1 – M36

Deliverable D5.1 – Dissemination and Communication Plan

		<p>content, in the form of a comprehensive digital handbook.</p> <p>4. Participation in conferences, exhibitions, and collaborative events with other EU projects.</p> <p>5. Maintaining an active and engaging presence on social media platforms like LinkedIn, targeting the general public as well as industry stakeholders and policy makers.</p>		
5.3	Produce and publish a final publishable report on Dissemination and Communication	Produce and publish the final publishable report will present key results, main lessons learnt, and recommendations for the future. It will be professionally designed, attractive, and tailored to the target group. The content and final draft must be discussed with CINEA before publication.	<p>Lead: HiG</p> <p>Support: All Partners</p>	M32 – M34

1.5. Deliverables

Deliverable	Title	Type	Dissemination Level	Responsibility	Deadline
5.1	Dissemination and Communication Plan	R – Document, report	PU - Public	PES	M3
5.2	Mid-term Communication and Dissemination Report	R – Document, report	PU - Public	PES	M19

Deliverable D5.1 – Dissemination and Communication Plan

5.3	Draft Publishable Report on Dissemination and Communication Draft	R Document, report	SEN - Sensitive	HiG	M33
5.4	Final Publishable Report on Dissemination and Communication	R Document, report	PU - Public	HiG	M34

1.6. Milestones

Milestone	Title	Verification	Responsibility	Deadline
21	Website Launch	Website link	HiG	M4
22	Launch of social media accounts	Link to social media accounts	e7	M6

1.7. Efforts

Participant	Efforts
Polar Energy Solutions AB	7
Högskolan i Gävle	6,24
Linköpings universitet	0,75
Politecnico di Milano	3,07
e7 GMBH	5,68
Nordic Energy Audit AB	0,75
Total personal-months	23,49

1.8. Long term vision

The strategic long-term objective is to ensure the results of the E4S project are not limited to the project's lifetime, but also after the funding period ends. To drive the clean energy transition forward within the supply chain of the manufacturing sector, by focusing on enhancing the energy efficiency of the small- and medium sized enterprise (SME) suppliers, essentially enabling a faster pace towards a green transition and decarbonization in the manufacturing sector.

Results such as the novel certification scheme tailored specifically for SMEs, which simplifies and enhances the assessment of energy efficiency together with the concrete handbook and the one-stop-shop to become a natural part of the manufacturing sectors day-to-day processes.

2. Structured approach

2.1. Methodology

The dissemination and communication of the project will, at the core, be the responsibility of all project partners while the coordination of the work is led by Polar Energy Solutions (PES). A working group comprised of participants from all project beneficiaries will meet regularly online, once a month to monitor progress, identify next steps, gather input and discuss content. All dissemination and communication will be done through the project official channels, and each partner is responsible for further sharing the content through their own channels and networks where relevant.

2.2. Stakeholders and target groups

To produce and execute effective dissemination and communication throughout the project life cycle it is crucial that the project identify the key target groups and stakeholders. This has been followed up by a deeper stakeholder analysis that will be continuously reviewed by the dissemination and communication working group as new input is collected and documented. It will function as a basis for how the project will interact with each stakeholder group individually in order to achieve effective dissemination and communication results.

Dissemination and communication content and activities will be designed to target each key target group and stakeholder based on the most effective way of reaching them and in an impactful way ensure that they obtain the information.

An initial list of likely target groups and stakeholders was developed in the proposal phase of the project and a final list is presented below:

No	Target audience	Description
1	Focal Companies	These companies are central to the project's scope and objectives. They are the main beneficiaries and can offer invaluable insights into the operational challenges and opportunities around energy audits and renewable energy adoption. They help to ensure the project's relevance and effectiveness in real-world business environments.
2	EU Policy Makers	This group is crucial as they shape the regulations that govern energy usage and sustainability measures. Their involvement can provide policy-level backing and help align the project with existing EU frameworks like the Energy Efficiency Directive and the Renewable Energy Directive.
3	Industry Associations	They can offer a broader industry perspective, helping to generalize the findings and ensuring that the measures are realistic and implementable at a larger scale.

4	Financial Institutions	Access to finance is often a key barrier. By involving financial institutions, you can explore various models for funding energy efficiency and renewable energy projects.
5	Research Organisations and Academic Partners	These stakeholders offer technical expertise and can validate the scientific integrity of the project. They can also provide research resources that smaller companies may not have access to.
6	Member State Agencies	Agencies have a keen interest in reducing the energy footprint of businesses within their jurisdiction. They can provide regulatory insights, and their endorsement could serve as a powerful motivator for businesses to implement the recommendations of energy audits.
7	Energy offices	As a key stakeholder in terms of increasing uptake and implementation of new knowledge and technology by societal actors it is key to ensure communication and dissemination that reaches this group. Energy offices consult societal actors, companies and institutions about energy management.
8	Grid owners	Have a vested interest in what is going on in their grids, and how customers are dealing with challenges to their operations associated with the grid.
9	Students and future leaders	Students and future leaders can bring new knowledge into real life operations.
10	Small- and medium sized enterprise suppliers	These companies are central to the project's scope and objectives. They are the main beneficiaries and can offer invaluable insights into the operational challenges and opportunities around energy audits and renewable energy adoption. They help to ensure the project's relevance and effectiveness in real-world business environments.
11	Energy suppliers	Have a vested interest in their customer behaviour and how customers are dealing with challenges to their operations associated with the energy consumption.

2.3. Dissemination and communication levels

Dissemination and communication will be executed on three different levels, on a local, a national and on an international level. The intent is to effectively reach as many relevant stakeholders as possible and ensure that the message is understood on all levels. This also ensures that the project is able to gather input from relevant stakeholders on all levels about its work that enables the project to adapt and overcome barriers and more effectively reach project objectives during the project life cycle.

The project will make use of the geographical distribution of project beneficiaries where possible in order to participate in and execute effective dissemination and

communication. Project beneficiaries will be responsible for dissemination and communication with local and national stakeholders within their own EU member state and international dissemination and communication with stakeholders will be coordinated within the dissemination and communication working group.

2.4. Dissemination and communication channels

The project will deploy a number of relevant channels to effectively achieve its dissemination and communication objectives. Each channel has been tailored to target one or more of the identified stakeholders and target groups in a strategic and effective manner on the basis of the stakeholder analysis.

No	Channel	Description	Stakeholder and Target group
1	Website	Project website that communicates and disseminate about the project, its objectives, activities and results.	All stakeholders and target groups.
2	Newsletter	Digital newsletter that is published on the project website and shared through social media accounts and e-mail mailing lists.	All stakeholders and target groups.
3	Social media	Social media accounts that, in a relevant way, are able to effectively reach and inform specific stakeholders and target groups. This will be continuously evaluated throughout the project life cycle.	All stakeholders and target groups.
4	Workshops	Workshops held to drive progress forward together with key stakeholders.	Focal companies, Research Organisations and Academic Partners, Small- and medium sized enterprise suppliers.
5	Conferences	Participate in relevant conferences to communicate and disseminate results to relevant stakeholders.	EU Policy Makers, Industry Associations, Research Organisations and Academic Partners, Member State Agencies.
6	Exhibitions	Participate in relevant exhibitions to communicate and disseminate results to relevant stakeholders.	Industry Associations, Research Organisations and Academic Partners, Member State Agencies.
7	Presentations	Present the project and project results to relevant stakeholders.	EU Policy Makers, Industry Associations, Financial institutions, Member State

			Agencies, Energy offices, Grid owners, students and future leaders, Small- and medium sized enterprise suppliers.
8	Liason with EU projects and clusters	Interact with EU projects and clusters where relevant to communicate and disseminate results to relevant stakeholders.	EU Policy Makers, Research Organisations and Academic Partners.

2.5. Working group

A working group comprised of participants from all project beneficiaries and led by Polar Energy Solutions will meet regularly online, once a month. The objective of the working group is, in a collective and coordinated way, to monitor progress, identify next steps, gather input and discuss content and actions to be taken by the consortium. Each Consortium partner will participate in most dissemination and communication activities at some capacity, distributing information both internally within the organisation and externally towards key stakeholders.

3. Dissemination activities

3.1. Dissemination activities

The following table shows dissemination activities to be carried out during the project.

No	Activity	Description	Stakeholders	Responsibility	Indicator
1	Scientific publications	Scientific results are published in academic publications	Research Organisations and Academic Partners	Lead: HiG Support: academic partners	All 3 published scientific publications
2	Workshops	Workshops are held to drive progress forward together with key stakeholders on a number of key topics.	Focal companies, Research Organisations and Academic Partners, Small- and medium sized enterprise suppliers	Lead: HiG Support: partners	All 12 workshops over 36 months
3	Trainings / webinars	Trainings / webinars are held to ensure that key stakeholders learn how to adopt new knowledge and generate expected impact.	Focal Companies, EU Policy Makers, Industry Associations, Research Organisations and Academic Partners, Energy offices, Small- and medium sized enterprise suppliers	Lead: HiG Support: partners	All 6 sessions over 36 months
4	Handbook	A digital handbook containing guidelines and description of how to work with energy management in a supply chain is	Research Organisations and Academic Partners, Focal Companies, EU Policy Makers, Industry Associations, Small- and	Lead: HiG Support: partners	All 1 digital handbook published

		generated and made accessible to key stakeholders.	medium sized enterprise suppliers		
5	One-stop shop	Centralized online resource	Research Organisations and Academic Partners, Focal Companies, Industry Associations, Small- and medium sized enterprise suppliers Policy makers, General public	Lead: HiG Support: All partners	1 published one stop-shop website, regularly updated, becoming a key resource

3.2. Scientific publication guidelines

Acknowledgement for all scientific publications is mandatory. The following sentence, or similar is recommended: "This work has been supported by the E4S LIFE project, which has received funding from the European Union's LIFE under grant agreement No 101167263".

In all cases, project name and number, LIFE Programme and the European Union are compulsory and must be mentioned. Without the acknowledgement, the publication cannot be considered as a project activity.

All journal and congress publications must be included in the repository on the shared project server.

4. Communication activities

The following table shows communication activities to be carried out during the project.

No	Activity	Description	Stakeholders	Responsibility	Indicators & Reach
1	Corporate identity	Logotype, PowerPoint template, Word template etc.	All stakeholders and target groups.	Lead: e7 Support: All partners	Templates
2	Website	A project website is published and maintained continuously as new material is generated.	All stakeholders and target groups.	Lead: HiG Support: All partners	1 Website published 2000 visitors over 36 months
3	Newsletter	Publish a newsletter every six months communicating current project progress.	All stakeholders and target groups.	Lead: PES Support: All partners	6 newsletters published 100 addressee list over 36 months
4	Social media	Set up an active presence on social media accounts where best to reach identified stakeholders such as LinkedIn etc.	All stakeholders and target groups.	Lead: e7 Support: All partners	Set up at least 1 active social media account 100 followers over 36 months
5	Conferences	Participate in relevant conferences to communicate and disseminate results to relevant stakeholders.	EU Policy Makers, Industry Associations, Research Organisations and Academic Partners, Member State Agencies.	Lead: PES Support: All partners	Attend 3 conferences

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6	Exhibitions	Participate in relevant exhibitions to communicate and disseminate results to relevant stakeholders.	Industry Associations, Research Organisations and Academic Partners, Member State Agencies.	Lead: PES Support: All partners	Attend exhibitions 3
7	Presentations	Present the project and project results to relevant stakeholders.	EU Policy Makers, Industry Associations, Financial institutions, Member State Agencies, Energy offices, Grid owners, students and future leaders, Small- and medium sized enterprise suppliers.	Lead: PES Support: All partners	Present times 4

5. Timeline

5.1. M1 – M12

No	Activity	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12
1	Scientific publications												
2	Workshops												
3	Trainings / webinars												
4	Handbook												
5	One-stop shop												
6	Corporate identity												
7	Website												
8	Newsletter												
9	Social media												
10	Conferences												
11	Exhibitions												
12	Presentations												

5.2. M13 – M24

No	Activity	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24
1	Scientific publications												
2	Workshops												
3	Trainings / webinars												
4	Handbook												
5	One-stop shop												
6	Corporate identity												
7	Website												
8	Newsletter												
9	Social media												
10	Conferences												
11	Exhibitions												
12	Presentations												

5.3. M25 – M36

No	Activity	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36
1	Scientific publications												
2	Workshops												
3	Trainings / webinars												
4	Handbook												
5	One-stop shop												
6	Corporate identity												
7	Website												
8	Newsletter												
9	Social media												
10	Conferences												
11	Exhibitions												
12	Presentations												

6. Visibility — European flag and funding statement

6.1. Logotypes

Beneficiaries of EU funding shall use the European emblem in their communication to acknowledge the support received under EU programmes as well as (in this case) the Life programme logotype.

Unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate).

The emblem must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands or text. Apart from the emblem, no other visual identity or logo may be used to highlight the EU support. When displayed in association with other logos (e.g. of beneficiaries or sponsors), the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos

European Union Flag	
European Union Flag and Funding statement	Funded by the European Union
Life Programme Logotype	

The emblems shall be associated with a sentence. It should look something like this (whenever feasible): *Energy4Supply has received funding from the European Union's LIFE23-CET-BUSINESS programme under grant agreement No 101167263.*

The European emblems can be downloaded from the following Europa websites [EU flag | European Union](#) and [EU flag and Funding statement European Union, Communication and GDPR rules - European Commission](#).

6.2. Quality of information – Disclaimer

Any communication or dissemination activity related to the action must use factually accurate information. Moreover, it must indicate the following disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate):

"Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency, CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them."

7. Public Project Deliverables

Project deliverables that are to be publicly made available on the E4S project website and Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>).

Deliverable	Titel	WP	Lead	Type	Dissemination Level	Deadline
D3.1	Financial solutions Review Report	WP3	HiG	R – Document, report	PU - Public	M9
D3.4	Guidelines for SSCF document & Report on practical application on case	WP3	POLIMI	R – Document, report	PU - Public	M30
D3.5	Open Access Scientific Article	WP3	POLIMI	R – Document, report	PU - Public	M30
D4.1	Open Access Scientific Articles	WP4	LiU	R – Document, report	PU - Public	M30
D4.2	Business Model Solutions Report	WP4	LiU	R – Document, report	PU - Public	M36
D4.3	Supply Chain Energy Management Policy Program Handbook	WP4	HiG	R – Document, report	PU - Public	M36
D4.4	One-stop-shop Platform	WP4	HiG	DEC – Websites, patent filings, videos, etc	PU - Public	M36
D5.1	Dissemination and	WP5	PES	R – Document	PU - Public	M3

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	Communication Plan			nt, report		
D5.2	Mid-term Communication and Dissemination Report	WP5	PES	R – Document, report	PU - Public	M19
D5.4	Final Publishable Report on Dissemination and Communication	WP5	HiG	R – Document, report	PU - Public	M34
D6.1	Sustainability Plan	WP6	HiG	R – Document, report	PU - Public	M6
D6.2	Extract of Project Data from the LIFE KPI Web Tool	WP6	HiG	DATA – data sets, microdata, etc	PU - Public	M36
D6.3	Replication Strategy Document	WP6	LiU	R – Document, report	PU - Public	M12
D6.4	Exploitation Plan	WP6	HiG	R – Document, report	PU - Public	M18
D6.5	Exploitation and Business Model Report	WP6	HiG	R – Document, report	PU - Public	M30
D6.6	After-LIFE Conservation Plan	WP6	HiG	R – Document, report	PU - Public	M36

8. Consortium Members

University of Gävle	<p>The logo of the University of Gävle features a stylized 'U' shape composed of two curved lines, one blue on the left and one yellow on the right, meeting at a red dot at the top. Below the graphic, the text 'UNIVERSITY OF GÄVLE' is written in a bold, black, sans-serif font.</p>
Polar Energy Solutions AB	<p>The logo for PolarEnergy consists of a dark blue square with a white cross-like shape inside, where the top-right and bottom-left quadrants are missing. Below the graphic, the text 'PolarEnergy' is written in a bold, sans-serif font, with 'Polar' in dark blue and 'Energy' in green.</p>
Linköpings universitet	<p>The logo for Linköping University features the letters 'li.u' in a bold, black, sans-serif font. To the right of the letters, the words 'LINKÖPING UNIVERSITY' are written in a smaller, black, sans-serif font, stacked on two lines.</p>
Politecnico di Milano	<p>The logo for Politecnico di Milano includes a circular seal on the left containing a figure and the year '1863'. To the right of the seal, the text 'POLITECNICO MILANO 1863' is written in a bold, black, sans-serif font.</p>
e7 GMBH	<p>The logo for e7 GMBH features a stylized 'e7' where the 'e' is orange and the '7' is grey. To the right of the graphic, the text 'ENERGY INNOVATION ENGINEERING' is written in a bold, black, sans-serif font, stacked on three lines.</p>
Nordic Energy Audit AB	<p>The logo for Nordic Energy Audit features a blue circular icon with a white plug symbol. To the right of the icon, the text 'NORDIC ENERGY AUDIT' is written in a bold, blue, sans-serif font, with 'MANAGE YOUR ENERGY' in a smaller, blue, sans-serif font below it.</p>

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